

D1.2 System requirements and data spaces framework and architecture

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Flex4Res members of consortium

Table 1 Consortium members

Partner name	Shortcode	Website link
PANEPISTIMIO PATRON	LMS	https://lms.mech.upatras.gr/
VOESTALPINE HIGH PERFORMANCE METALS DIGITAL SOLUTIONS GMBH	VOE	https://www.voestalpine.com/group/en/
SIDENOR VIOMICHANIKI CHALYVA ANONYMI ETAIRIA	SID	https://sidenor.gr/en/
HANS BERG GMBH&CO KG	HANS	https://www.berg-kg.de/de/
GOIMEK S COOP	GOI	https://www.goimek.com/es
SORALUCE S. COOP.	SOR	https://www.soraluce.com/en
EIT MANUFACTURING CENTRAL GGMBH	EITM	https://www.eitmanufacturing.eu/
NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT SA	INTRA	https://www.netcompany-intrasoft.com/
CONTACT SOFTWARE GMBH	CONT	https://contact-software.com/
A1 DIGITAL INTERNATIONAL GMBH	A1	https://www.a1.digital/
BEIA	BEIA	https://beia.be/
SAVVY DATA SYSTEMS SL	SAV	https://www.savvydatasystems.com/es/inicio
MONDRAGON CORPORACION COOPERATIVA SCOOP	MON	https://www.mondragon-corporation.com/
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	TU Wien	http://www.ift.at/
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT DARMSTADT	TUDa	https://www.ptw.tu-darmstadt.de/
UNIVERSITAET SIEGEN	USI	https://www.uni-siegen.de/start/
IDEKO S COOP	IDE	https://www.ideko.es/

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List of Abbreviations

Table 2 List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AAS	Asset Administration Shell
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CAD	Computer Assisted Design
CBR	Case Based Reasoning
CNC	Computerized Numerical Control
DRS	Delay Recording System
EAF	Electric Arc Furnace
EC	European Commission
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
EU	European Union
FO	Fabrication Order
GA	Grant agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HQ	Headquarters
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IDS	International Data Spaces
IF	Induction Furnace
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IoT	Internet of Things
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
PAC	Programmable Automation Controller
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
TBD	To be Determined
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
DMP	Data Management Plan
WP	Work package
FAIR	Findable, Accesible, Interoperable and Re-usable
B2B	Business-to-business
WPL	Work package leader
PPR	Product, Process & Resources

Executive summary

This document presents the system requirements for the Flex4Res platform along with its architecture. For each use case the system requirements were gathered using the [INCOSE Guide V3.1](#) and ISO/IEC 29148 (section 2). In brief for all use cases 62 functional requirements were identified along with the relevant hardware and software for each use case. Moreover, the performance and non-functional requirements of each use case were defined.

The next step was to define the Flex4Res platform architecture based on IDS and GAIA-X.3.2 The main overview combines all the major components required to address the system requirements and is presented in section 3.2 (see Figure 12). A mapping between architecture components and system requirements can be found in Table 15.

The last step was to deliver more detailed documentation for all parts of the architecture. Sections 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, and 3.7 provide the descriptions on how the architecture components work, their APIs, and their internal structure. In addition, for those components that already exist as “off-the-shelf” implementations appropriate links to their documentation and APIs have been established. This document will serve as the common implementation guide for work packages 2, 3, and 4.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

D1.2 is a deliverable of WP1 of the Flex4Res project, which aims to provide further information about its architecture. Flex4Res project is built on top of the state-of-the-art Gaia-X and IDS technologies for data sharing in the horizontal supply chain and the Asset Administration Shell (AAS) to implement intra factory reconfiguration practices. The project considers the Digital Twin of the value-adding network a key enabling technology to achieve reconfiguration processes in highly flexible production systems and networks. Moreover, architectures and an explanation of the main components of the architecture is provided, i.e., the resilience assessment toolbox and the reconfiguration strategies toolbox.

1.2 Objectives

The objective of this deliverable is to provide an architecture of the project, explain the subcomponents, and map them to the components that have been identified to the D1.1 for each use case respectively. Additionally, the system requirements of each use case are reported as well, and they were mapped with the validation scenarios that have been defined for each use case in D1.1 as well.

1.3 Deliverable requirements

The deliverable is organized into four sections. It starts with an introduction to the deliverable and the main objectives of this document. Secondly, the System requirements section is divided into four subsections, one for each use case respectively. Thirdly, is presented the Flex4Res architecture and a description of the architecture. Also, in this section the IoT platforms, Digital Twins, Asset Administration Shell concept, Dataspaces, Connectors, Resilience assessment toolbox architecture (WP3), and Reconfiguration strategy architecture (WP4) are presented. Finally, the last section is the conclusion of this document along with future steps. This deliverable will be used for the upcoming Work Packages for the implementations and integration of the architecture into each use case. Parts of Deliverable D1.1 “Industrial pilots’ requirements and specifications” were used mostly in section 2, to present the system requirements of the Flex4Res use cases.

2 System requirements

The idea is to get a common sense of the system requirements in order to develop a proper Flex4Res Architecture and -toolbox.

The system requirements were defined according to the [INCOSE Guide V3.1](#) and ISO/IEC 29148. Characteristics should be:

- **Necessary:** Every requirement statement is necessary.
- **Implementation Independent:** A requirement states what is required, not how the requirement is met.
- **Unambiguous:** A requirement statement lends itself to a single interpretation.
- **Complete:** A requirement statement is complete in and of itself.
- **Singular:** A requirement statement addresses a single thought.
- **Feasible:** A requirement statement expresses something that is inherently feasible.
- **Verifiable:** A requirement statement is verifiable.
- **Correct:** A requirement statement is a correct expression of the stakeholder expectation.

- **Conforming:** A requirement statement conforms to standards selected as applicable to the organization.

The following sections will define the specific requirements per Use-Case that provide a basis for the (1) architecture definition and (2) software development.

Apply the INCOSE rules:

- **Precision**
 - E.g. Use definite articles
 - Use active voice with actor clearly identified
- **Concision**
 - Avoid superfluous infinitives
- **Non-Ambiguity**
 - Use correct grammar
- **Singularity**
 - Write a simple affirmative declarative sentence, conditioned and qualified by relevant sub-clauses.

2.1 Use Case Structure

2.1.1 Overview

- Brief description of the use case and its purpose.
A clear and concise description should be provided of the use case and what it is intended to achieve. This should include information about the problem or need that the use case addresses, as well as any specific goals or outcomes that the use case is designed to deliver.
- A brief overview of the system elements and actors.
Identify the key system elements and actors that are involved in the use case. This should include any hardware, software, or other components that are necessary for the use case to function, as well as any users or other stakeholders who interact with the system.
- Information about the objectives should also be included, and any high-level constraints or assumptions.
Details about the objectives that the use case is designed to achieve should be provided. This should include information about any specific requirements or constraints that need to be taken into account, as well as any assumptions that have been made about the system or its environment. Examples of high-level constraints or assumptions might include limitations on available resources, restrictions on the types of technology that can be used, or assumptions about user behaviour or preferences.
- *E.g., This use case involves a customer selecting and purchasing a product online from a web store.*

2.1.2 Functional requirements

- A description of the system or system elements functions or tasks to be performed by the system to support the use case.
Identify the specific functions or tasks that the system or system elements will need to perform to support the use case. These functions or tasks should be described in detail, including any inputs or outputs required, as well as any relevant dependencies or relationships with other system components.
- A description of performance requirements of those functions quantitatively.
The performance requirements for each function or task should be defined in a quantitative manner. This might include information about the expected response time, throughput, or accuracy of each function or task. It may also include information about any relevant standards or regulations that must be met, as well as any specific testing or validation requirements.

- *E.g., The system must allow customers to create and manage their user accounts. The system must provide customers with a catalogue of products that they can browse and search.*

2.1.2.1 System Elements

- The specific system elements that are required to implement the use case should be identified. This may include hardware components, software modules, and communication protocols.
- The specific hardware components that are required to implement the use case should be identified. This may include servers, network devices, sensors, actuators, and other physical devices.
- The specific software modules that are required to implement the use case should be identified. This may include operating systems, databases, middleware, application servers, and other software components.
- The specific communication protocols that are required to implement the use case should be identified. This may include network protocols, messaging protocols, and other communication mechanisms.
- *E.g., web server, database server, payment gateway*

2.1.2.2 Performance Requirements

- The performance requirements that the system must meet to support the use case must be specified. This may include response times, processing speeds, and data transfer rates.
- The acceptable ranges for each performance requirement should be defined.
- Any constraints or limitations that may affect the performance of the system should be described.
- Any performance testing or monitoring requirements that will be necessary to ensure that the system meets the required performance levels should be specified. *E.g., The system must load the catalogue page within 3 seconds of the customer's request.*

2.1.3 Non-functional requirements

- This section should define the "-ilities" to include as non-functional requirements. The non-functional aspects of the system that are necessary to support the use case should be identified. Examples of "-ilities" to consider include:
 - Availability: the system should be available for use when needed
 - Reliability: the system should function correctly and consistently
 - Maintainability: the system should be easy to maintain and update
 - Scalability: the system should be able to handle increased loads or data volumes
 - Usability: the system should be easy to learn and use
 - Security: the system should be secure against unauthorized access or attacks
 - Performance: the system should perform at an acceptable level under expected workloads
 - Interoperability: the system should be able to work with other systems or technologies
 - Consider any other "-ilities" that are relevant to the use case.
- In addition, any other non-functional aspects that are necessary to support the use case should be defined.
- Measures for quality requirements should be defined:
For each non-functional requirement, identify how it will be measured or evaluated. Examples include:

- Availability: the system should be available for a certain percentage of time (e.g., 99.9% uptime)
 - Reliability: the system should have a low rate of failures or errors (e.g., less than 1%)
 - Maintainability: the system should have a low mean time to repair (MTTR) or mean time between failures (MTBF)
 - Scalability: the system should be able to handle a certain number of users or transactions (e.g., 1000 simultaneous users)
 - Usability: the system should have a high user satisfaction rating (e.g., 80% or higher)
 - Security: the system should have a low rate of security incidents (e.g., less than 1 per month)
 - Performance: the system should meet certain performance criteria (e.g., respond to requests within 2 seconds)
 - Interoperability: the system should be able to exchange data with other systems using specified standards or protocols.
 - Define any other quality measures that are relevant to the non-functional requirements of the use case.
- *E.g., The system must provide a responsive and user-friendly interface that can handle concurrent user traffic.*

2.2 Voestalpine

2.2.1 Overview

The purpose of the use case is based on the integration of various manufacturing assets to apply flexible and agility to manufacturing processes and is based on existing production environment information. VOE address the Meso level (Production Line) with a dedicated link to the Macro level and the Micro Level.

Figure 1 Exploration level of VOE for “Steel Processing”

A vision for VOE is integrating flexible and agile matrix production that enables the reconfiguration of the manufacturing process during production. This will be enabled by the agile reconfiguration of production flow tackled within this project. VOE expects a reduction of lead times and, therefore, delivery times. Within the project a new shop floor modelling approach will be introduced and include machine capability and current configuration status data into a product, process, and resource model. Based on this a reconfiguration mechanism will be adopted, enabling a flexible flow of products through the factory, and a new agile production schema, and being able to adapt fast to disruptions on the shopfloor, but also disruptions coming from the supply chain. The new resilience toolbox services allow to evaluate missing capabilities and need for reconfiguration.

Figure 2 Generic picture as base fundamental for VOE

To make the process more resilient, new systems are being introduced that also support the reconfiguration of tools. The goal is to develop and integrate a tool that can detect errors through sensors and assess them through case-based reasoning and, if necessary, suggest necessary measures for reconfiguration. This smart reconfiguration toolbox for sensor is being designed to optimize the whole process and must be executable on Industrial Edge device solution which is already in use.

The considered production process of the use case starts with the warehouse process and runs over sawing up to grinding. The production process for added value starts normally with cutting on a bandsaw or in very less cases on a circular saw. The type of technical details varies in a wide range. These variations will be considered in the configuration capabilities. Key elements are physical assets, information (e.g. Order details, layout, etc.), capability matrix for execution and Edge devices as execution element for processing.

The following technical and functional and generally described and represent a public version.

2.2.2 Functional requirements

Table 3 presents the high-level technical requirements

Table 3 High-level technical requirements for VOE use case

#	Application domain	Description of the requirement
R1	Condition diagnosis cycles	The data about the current states should be included in the whole system to provide resilience. Integration of information and decision taking
R2	Communication	AAS models for the machines and scheduling
R3	Scheduling capabilities	System should be able to generate and propose modifications over existing production schedules, while achieving the same or improved end goal (e.g., work order deadlines, cost)
R4	Connectivity & integration	System should be able to interface with all involved systems and data sources and retrieve usable data from them.

R5	Integration	No data interfacing to external resources and dependencies in development and operations
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Having as an input the high-level technical requirements and use case scenarios described in Table 4 presents the list of the detailed system functional requirements for each validation scenario:

Table 4 VOE use case functional requirements examples

#	Functional requirement description	Sub-Component
VOE 1	The system must be able to access asset information direct via interface from manufacturing assets.	Integration of AAS / Data Layer
VOE 2	The system must have the capability to integrate seamlessly into the existing IoT Platform.	Integration of AAS / Visualization Layer
VOE 3	The system must be fully compatible with HTML5, ensuring seamless rendering and functionality across web browsers and devices.	Integration of AAS / Visualization Layer
VOE 4	The system must be able to visually represent raw data on the user graphical user interface (GUI) within the execution layer (on Edge layer). This visualization should provide clear and meaningful representations of the data for effective analysis and decision-making.	Integration of AAS / Visualization Layer
VOE 5	The system must provide a human-machine interface (HMI) specifically designed for data configuration and adaptation on the Edge Layer. This interface should allow users to easily configure and adapt the system's data parameters and settings in a user-friendly and intuitive manner.	Integration of AAS / Visualization Layer
VOE 6	The system must have the capability to visualize raw data and generate Key Performance Indicator (KPI) dashboards according to user requirements.	Integration of AAS / Visualization Layer
VOE 7	The system must be able to execute containerized applications on both edge devices and centrally manage them.	Integration of AAS / Architectural requirements
VOE 8	The system must be based on a software platform that facilitates the deployment, configuration, and management of Industrial Edge devices, ensuring compatibility and leveraging the features and capabilities.	Integration of AAS / Architectural requirements
VOE 9	The system must be designed to accommodate and support various hardware components from typical Edge Device portfolio, ensuring compatibility and seamless integration with different types of devices.	Integration of AAS / Architectural requirements
VOE 10	The system must utilize software containers that conform to typical Edge Device Architecture, specifically employing Docker technology. This ensures efficient deployment, management, and scalability of applications.	Integration of AAS / Architectural requirements
VOE 11	The system must support seamless integration into secure authentication processes.	Integration of AAS / Architectural requirements
VOE 12	The system must provide data interfaces based on API technology to establish seamless connectivity with ERP Systems.	Integration of AAS / Architectural requirements
VOE 13	The system must have the capability to store data in a dedicated database. This ensures efficient storage, retrieval, and analysis of time-stamped data for various operational and analytical purposes.	Integration of AAS / Architectural requirements
VOE 14	The system must support data storage on the Edge device itself, enabling the local storage of data for immediate processing, analysis, and offline operation.	Integration of AAS / Architectural requirements
VOE 15	The system must provide the capability to configure PPR elements, which include Product, Process, and Resources. This functionality allows users to define and customize the characteristics, attributes, and parameters associated with products, processes, and resources within the system.	Develop shopfloor model, e.g., PPR / software components

VOE 16	The system must support data exchange with external supplier or other relevant stakeholders.	Integration of AAS / software components
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2.2.3 Non-functional requirements

The following non-functional requirements must be applicable:

- **Risk management** for cloud infrastructure (e.g. Evaluation matrix and decision matrix)
- **Offline functionality** (not reliable on interface to external systems)
- **Maintenance cycle** without stable external connection
- **Availability:** the system should be available for the majority (99%) of time
- **Reliability:** the system should have a very low rate (**1%**) of failures or errors
- **Scalability:** the system should be able to handle 200 number of users
- **Interoperability:** The system has a standardized API and data model in order to provide access to the data.
- **Security:** the system must be secure against unauthorized access or attacks (99%)

2.3 Sidenor

2.3.1 Overview

Sidenor produces a large variety of steel products (i.e., wire rod coils, rebar coils, straight rebar, profiles etc.) that are used in many industrial sectors. Sidenor’s plant in Thessaloniki produces a wide range of steel products in various shapes, dimensions and quality specifications. The plant started in 1962 and it is the first production plant of the company.

LMS and INTRA will act as technical partners of the Sidenor use case. LMS is acting as a resilience assessment, microplanning and macroplanning technology provide for the SIDENOR use case and INTRA is acting as a systems integrator and software developer for the SIDENOR use case.

The as-is scenario of Sidenor was defined in the “D1.1 – Industrial pilots’ requirements and specifications” and presented in Figure 3. The as-is scenario illustrates the process in Sidenor in order to compute the production schedule of Sidenor plant. Data from SAP and SAP-IBP (Sidenor HQ) are used in order to compute the production schedule for Thessaloniki’s plant.

Figure 3 Sidenor As-is Scenario

Figure 4 illustrate the to-be scenario that was defined in the “D1.1 – Industrial pilots’ requirements and specifications” for the Sidenor use case. The to-be scenario is using the Flex4res data space in order to

transfer data between the Sidenor HQ, Thessaloniki’s plant, Resilience assessment toolbox and Reconfiguration strategies toolbox. Moreover, the components and sub-components of the Sidenor use case are presented in Figure 5 as well, where the main components of the solution are the IDS/ Gaia-X data space, Resilience assessment toolbox and Reconfiguration strategies toolbox. The data that will be used in the to-be scenario are data from SAP and SAP-IBP. Additionally, Figure 4 presents the to-be architecture of the Sidenor use case.

Figure 4 Sidenor To-Be Scenario

The Production scheduler and MPS tools aim to result an accurate production schedule and master production schedule in order to improve the KPIs that Sidenor defined in the “D1.1 – Industrial pilots’ requirements and specifications” section 2.2.2.4. The goal of the MPS is to use data from the SAP-IBP (demand planning) and SAP in order to compute a master production schedule. In order to compute the production schedule, the demand planning, supply planning, data from SAP will be used to compute the production schedule for Sidenor plant. Additionally, in order to compute the production schedule, the Macro-Meso transition tool should be used to disaggregate the information from product families (SKU groups, coming from MPS) to SKUs (input for production schedule). Moreover, data from MPS, SAP and SAP-IBP will be used to assess the resilience the supply chain. Furthermore, in order to assess the resilience in the factory level, data from Macro-Meso transition tool and Production scheduler will be used.

Figure 5 Components of solutions at Sidenor

2.3.2 Functional requirements

The requirements in Table 5 were defined in “D1.1 – Industrial pilots’ requirements and specifications” and present the challenges and gaps that Sidenor aims to overcome during the Flex4Res project.

Table 5 High-level technical requirements for Sidenor use case

#	Application domain	Description of the requirement
R1	Need for overall robust planning strategy to both network and factory level that results to maximized accuracy of production schedule.	A robust planning strategy at both network and factory levels is crucial for maximizing the accuracy of production schedules. It ensures efficient coordination across all facilities and operations, optimizing resource utilization and minimizing lead times. This approach enhances operational efficiency, improves customer

		satisfaction through reliable delivery schedules, and enables better cost management by reducing wastage and inventory costs. Implementing advanced planning tools and data-driven insights facilitates agile responses to market changes, ensuring competitive advantage in dynamic business environments.
R2	Reducing computational time for optimal production scheduling	Reducing the computation time for production planning, currently handled manually by a planner, is essential for enhancing operational efficiency and responsiveness. Automating this process with advanced algorithms and AI-driven tools can streamline scheduling tasks, significantly reducing lead times and minimizing delays in production. By leveraging technology to optimize planning workflows, organizations can achieve faster decision-making, improve resource allocation, and adapt more swiftly to changes in demand or production constraints. This transformation not only enhances overall productivity but also empowers planners to focus on strategic initiatives rather than repetitive scheduling tasks, ultimately driving greater operational agility and competitiveness in the market
R3	Automated procedure to disaggregate from product families (SKU groups) to SKUs for production scheduling.	The design of a service that will disaggregate the information from product families (SKU groups) to SKUs will be designed and developed, to avoid potential manual errors.
R4	Automated process to transfer data	Provide a framework in order to transfer data in a safe way and by the use of standardized models.
R5	Implementing an integrated Master Production Scheduler for optimizing supply planning	Developing the Master Production Scheduler (MPS) to compute Supply Planning involves integrating data from SAP and SAP-IBP. This integration enables the MPS to leverage comprehensive datasets including demand forecasts, inventory levels, production capacities, and other critical factors. By utilizing data from SAP and SAP-IBP, the MPS can generate optimized master production schedules that align with real-time demand fluctuations and facilities availability. This approach not only enhances the accuracy and efficiency of production planning but also facilitates proactive decision-making and agile responses to changes in market conditions. Ultimately, the MPS serves as a pivotal tool in maximizing operational efficiency and ensuring that master production schedules are synchronized with corporate goals and customer demands.
R6	Maximize the profit of the company in terms of raising resilience level for both	To measure the resilience of a manufacturing system using the Proof of Concept (PoC) methodology, where the goal is to maximize the company's profit by

	macro and meso levels by defining certain scenarios in a cost-based approach by including profit as the key element to evaluate resilience and computing PoC	enhancing resilience at both macro and meso levels. This involves defining scenarios through a cost-based approach where profit serves as the primary metric for evaluating resilience. By leveraging PoC, the company can systematically assess the impact of changes on resilience, identifying optimal strategies that mitigate risks and enhance operational robustness. This methodology ensures that resilience investments not only protect against disruptions but also contribute to sustained profitability and competitiveness in the market.
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Having as an input the high-level technical requirements and use case scenarios described in the deliverable “D1.1 – Industrial pilots’ requirements and specifications”, Table 6 presents the list of the detailed system functional requirements for each validation scenario.

Table 6 Sidenor use case functional requirements

#	Functional requirement description	Sub-Component	Validation scenario
SID 1	Transfer data through data space	Integrate the AAS middleware that will capture all required data from the SAP and SAP-IBP and validate data sharing through the data spaces.	Scenario 3
SID2	Assess the resilience in supply chain and factory level (T3.2)	Design and develop resilience assessment tool for the supply chain and factory level	Scenario 4, Scenario 5
SID3	Visualise resilience assessment results to the user (GUI) and development of the GUI	Develop GUI	Scenario 4, Scenario 5
SID4	Use standardize AAS models and develop new additional models to capture all data from the SAP and SAP-IBP	Use existing, and develop new AAS models	Scenario 3
SID5	Design & develop Production scheduler	Design and develop the Production scheduler	Scenario 2
SID6	Design & develop Master production scheduler (MPS)	Design and develop the MPS	Scenario 1
SID7	Validate the performance of the Flex4Res solutions to the Sidenor use case	Validate that all tools work properly on top of the data space and AAS concept. The goal is to measure and compare the expected KPIs that were defined in the D1.1 (see 2.2.2.4 subsection) and actual KPIs that we will obtain.	Scenario 6
SID8	Visualise results of the MPS and Production scheduler through a GUI	Develop GUIs	Scenario 2, 3 & 6
SID9	Export result in an Excel	Download excel file from the Production scheduler GUI	Scenario 3
SID10	Define and create roles for accessing the functionalities of the tool	Develop GUI, MPS & Production scheduler	Scenario 1, Scenario 3, Scenario 4 & Scenario 5

2.3.2.1 System Elements

The following software and hardware components are deployed in Sidenor plants:

- **DRS RECORDING SYSTEM:** The Delay Recording System (DRS) is a delay recording system, where data are collected from sensors in production lines and produce event timelines.

- **LEVEL2 IF REPORT:** is a monitoring system of Induction Furnace (IF)
- **HMI RHF, HOT CHARGING LOGGING:** is a sensor, that is used to monitor and measure the percentage of the hot charging billet.
- **HMI HOOKS, WEIGHT LOGGING:** is a sensor that is used to monitor and measure the percentage of the billet's weight.
- **HMI COMPACTOR, COIL LENGTH LOGGING:** is a sensor that is used monitoring the measure the length of the coil.
- **ENERGY FROM SUB-STATION:** is a sensor that is used to measure electricity and natural gas consumption.
- **IBA HISTORICAL SERVER:** is used for monitoring electricity and to calculate torque.
- **SAP:** is an ERP where Sidenor store data. Data that will be used for the toolboxes will be get from the SAP.
- **SQL Expression DB:** Is a data database where Sidenor store information from sensors and daily report. The database in updated every 30 seconds.

2.3.2.2 Performance Requirements

The following performance requirements are applicable for the Sidenor use case:

- **Master production scheduler:** Correctly the MPS takes approximately 10 working days to be computed manually. The expected time to compute the Supply planning is estimated to 1 day.
- **Production scheduler:** Currently the production schedule takes 5 hours per week to be computed manually. The expected time to compute the production schedule for a day is estimated to 1 hour. Also, in case of rescheduling Sidenor needs 2 hours to find a new schedule. The Production schedule tool is expected to take 30 minutes to compute new schedule.
- **Resilience assessment tools:** The expected time to assess the resilience of a factory and network level is estimated to 1 hour.
- **Respond time of the UI:** The expected time to respond the UI to the user is 2-5 secs.

2.3.3 Non-functional requirements

The following non-functional requirements should be fulfilled by the Flex4Res platform:

- **Availability:** the system should be available for 99 % of time
- **Reliability:** the system should have a 1% rate of failures or errors
- **Scalability:** the system should be able to handle 100 number of users
- **Security:** the system should have 1% rate of security incidents
- **Interoperability:** The system has a standardized API and data model in order to provide access to the data of Sidenor.
- **Security:** the system should be secure against unauthorized access or attacks

2.4 Hans Berg

2.4.1 Overview

The company, Hans Berg GmbH & Co. KG, founded in 1950, has been a technology and market leader in the field of connection technology for panel radiators since 1970. Later on, Hans Berg started the production of airbag tubes. Leveraging its experience in the field of cold forming technology, Hans Berg developed the process chain for demanding components with high-quality requirements, including materials with high-strength and ultra-high-strength properties, in order to further expand the product

range. USI, IFT, PTW, Contact and Beia, together with Hans, are the partners involved in this use case, being USI the leader of the use case team.

The aim of the Hans Berg use case is to improve resilience at the machine level of the compound forming process by detecting errors in the tooling and assisting in the reconfiguration of the tooling.

Figure 6 To be scenario Hans Berg use case

To achieve the set goals, a reconfiguration toolbox is being developed, which is basically divided into two systems:

1. Smart Tool, which improves resilience to, for example, variations in material and actively detects the occurrence of errors that lead to tool reconfiguration options via AI - CBR.
2. Human Assistance system, which will create a feedback system that assists reconfiguration of tools using a virtual environment or digital twin of the press based on the outer geometry of the press and the geometry of the tools.

2.4.2 Functional requirements

The following tables present the high-level technical requirements of the main modules already described in the deliverable “D1.1 – Industrial pilots’ requirements and specifications”.

Table 7 High-level technical requirements for Hans Berg use case

#	Application domain	Description of the requirement
R1	Reconfiguration of the tools	Instead of manual identification, the system should identify the reconfiguration needs automatically in real time for the effective reconfiguration of the press and the tool; a decreasing of the downtime in this reconfiguration phase is expected by 10%.
R2	Visualization and virtualization	A visualization is expected for a worker that could assist him in performing the reconfiguration task directly in the press. This visualization elaborates the sequence and action of all the tasks needed to be performed in virtual environment. This virtual environment could be for example in Unity 3D, that may include digital twin of the press and the motions of the worker.
R3	Detection of Reconfiguration Needs	Detection of the faults in the individual forming stages and assessment by the fuzzy CBR for the reconfiguration decision.
R4	Flexible Tooling	New tool concept that is more resilient to material fluctuations. This can be achieved by using actuators in relevant tool areas, for example.

Having as an input the high-level technical requirements and use case scenarios described in the deliverable “D1.1 – Industrial pilots’ requirements and specifications”, the following table present the list of the detailed system functional requirements for each validation scenario:

Table 8 Hans Berg use case functional requirements

#	Functional requirement description	Sub-Component	Validation scenario
HANS1	The system must be able to retrieve and display real-time information about the status of the press	Smart Tool	Scenario 1
HANS 2	The system should be applicable to other presses	Smart Tool & Smart Reconfiguration	Scenario 1 & Scenario 2
HANS 3	The system should be transferable to other dies	Smart Tool	Scenario 1
HANS 4	The control unit must keep up with the production speed	Smart Tool	Scenario 1
HANS 5	The system should be easy to use and should not limit the worker in his/her activities	Smart Reconfiguration	Scenario 2
HANS 6	The assistance system should be accepted by workers	Smart Reconfiguration	Scenario 2
HANS 7	The system must withstand the surrounding conditions, which includes pollution due to dirt, vibrations, noise and heat development	Smart Tool, Smart & Reconfiguration	Scenario 1 & Scenario 2
HANS 8	The system must take advantage of the past decisions and actions of the workers	Smart Tool, Smart & Reconfiguration	Scenario 1 & Scenario 2
HANS 9	the system should be able to keep up with the typical tool lifetime	Smart Tool	Scenario 1

2.4.2.1 System Elements

Hardware Components

The following hardware components are deployed in the Hans Berg use case:

- **Edge Device**
A suitable edge device is selected for the resource-intensive applications. The edge device is used to make earlier data processing possible and leave room to add further applications.
- **Press**
The dies are installed on a Helmerdinger press, which can apply a force of 400t. The press is equipped with a Siemens S7 system.
- **Sensors**
A selection of sensors is integrated into the tool. They should collect relevant data to draw conclusions about potential faults in the process. The data is transmitted to the Edge device.
- **Dies**
For an alternative tool concept, the production of newly developed dies is necessary. The sensor technology is integrated into the tools and thus becomes part of the smart tool.

- **Hand Tools**
Hand tools, for example spanner, screw drivers, hammer, etc, to be used in the reconfiguration process
- **Controller**
The Q.station X controller from Gantner is used to record the sensor data. It has interfaces for CAN, Modbus TCP/IP, Modbus RTU, PROFIBUS, PROFINET and supports OPC UA, DDS and MQTT.
- **X-SENS Motion capturing sensors**
Recording the body movements of the worker to train the Human assistance system
- **Pupil Invisible eye tracking glasses**
Recording the eye movement of the worker to train the Human assistance system

Software modules

The following hardware modules are deployed in the Hans Berg use case:

- **PLC**
The PLC sends the collected data from the machine to the edge device.
- **Controller Software**
The GI.bench software is used to operate the controller. The GInsData API provides an unified platform independent interface to measurement data. This allows the python based fuzzy CBR to be integrated.

Communication protocols

The following communication protocols are used for the Hans Berg use case:

- **OPC-UA**
For communication between the machine and the edge device.
- **Instruction Protocol**
Instruction Protocol for reconfiguration with the aid of the Human Assistance system.
- **Error Management Protocol**
Defined protocols for the documentation of errors and error causes.
- **API**
API to communicate between the AI-CBR and Human Assistance System

2.4.2.2 Performance Requirements

The following performance requirements are applicable for the Hans Berg use case:

- **Smart Tool:** Selected faults from the large number of possible faults that can occur during production are processed during the course of the project. Features that could be the cause of these faults are monitored, e.g. by sensors installed in the mould. With this monitoring, in conjunction with the Fuzy-CBR, it should be possible to reduce the error detection time for selected errors by 10%.
- **Smart reconfiguration:** There are sometimes inconsistent error routines for the large number of possible errors in the forming or production of components. With smart reconfiguration, it should be possible to reduce the time required for selected tasks by 10% through standardised and clear instructions on how to proceed.

2.4.3 Non-functional requirements

The following non-functional requirements should be fulfilled by both main components (Smart Tool and Smart Reconfiguration):

- **Availability:** The system should be available for 99 % of time
- **Reliability:** The system should have a 1% rate of failures or errors
- **Scalability:** The system should be able to handle increased loads or data volumes.
- **Security:** The system should have a low rate of security incidents, less than 1 per month.
- **Interoperability:** The system should be able to work with other presses.
- **Security:** The system should be secure against unauthorized access or attacks.

2.5 Goimek

2.5.1 Overview

Goimek is specialized in high-accuracy part machining with the highest standards of quality and service. Goimek uses state-of-the-art technology and high precision, high output machines, complemented by the latest-generation verification resources. The Goimek factory, located at the Itziar plant, will provide the use case scenario for the developments of Flex4Res. Ideko, Mondragon, Savvy and Soraluce, together with Goimek, are the partners involved in this use case, with Ideko being the leader of the use case team.

The objective of the use case is to improve resilience at two levels: plant level and machine level. At the machine level, through machine condition and machining process improvement, monitoring and anomaly detection functionalities are applied. At plant level, through improvements in production planning and communication with the machine level.

Figure 7 Goimek Use Case architecture

Two main software components have been identified in the use case:

- Predictive Maintenance Module for Resilience, which will identify anomalies in both the machine and the machining process that could lead to failure.
- Production Planner for Reconfigurability, to optimize the scheduling at plant level by proposing reconfiguration strategies and alternate schedules if deadlines for planned work orders are at risk.

Figure 8 illustrates the components and subcomponents of these main modules.

Figure 8 (a) Predictive maintenance components and (b) Production planner components

2.5.2 Functional requirements

Table 9 and Table 10 present the high-level technical requirements of the main software modules already described in the deliverable “D1.1 – Industrial pilots’ requirements and specifications”.

Table 9 Goimek use case high-level technical requirements at the machine level

#	Application domain	Description of the requirement
R1	Condition diagnosis cycles	The cycles should give clear and understandable reports to the final user to help in the decision taking
R2	Condition diagnosis cycles	The cycles should give Key information to predict future failures or give early warnings of actual problems that are difficult to detect for the user
R3	Condition diagnosis cycles	The results of decisions should be included in the whole system to provide resilience. Integration of information and decision taking
R4	Virtualization, Digital Twins	AAS general and specific submodels to characterize the machines technical and operational data

Table 10 Goimek use case high-level technical requirements at the plant level

#	Application domain	Description of the requirement
R1	Scheduling capabilities	System should be able to generate and propose modifications over existing production schedules, while achieving the same or improved end goal (e.g., work order deadlines)

R2	Scheduling capabilities	System should be able to factor in aspects external to the producer company (e.g., arrival times of required parts & materials, finished parts logistics, etc.)
R3	Connectivity & integration	System should be able to interface with all involved systems and data sources and retrieve usable data from them.
R4	Virtualization, Digital Twins	AAS submodel to store the data exchanged with the enterprise-software systems (e.g. ERP) related with the machines

Having as an input the high-level technical requirements and use case scenarios described in the deliverable “D1.1 – Industrial pilots’ requirements and specifications”, Table 11 presents the list of the detailed system functional requirements for each validation scenario.

Table 11 Goimek use case functional requirements

#	Functional requirement description	Sub-Component	Validation scenario
GOI 1	The system must be able to retrieve and display real-time information about the status of the production equipment (machines/work centers) and machine components at shopfloor, through the IOT platform accessing sensors, PLCs and CNCs	Production Planner, Predictive Maintenance	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
GOI 2	The system must be able to integrate with other plant-level systems that manage the production schedule on a weekly basis	Production Planner	Scenario 1
GOI 3	The system must be able to retrieve information inserted by the operators working on the production equipment	Production Planner	Scenario 1
GOI 4	The system must be able to retrieve information about work orders, process routes, and availability of parts	Production Planner	Scenario 1
GOI 5	The system must be able to retrieve the currently active production schedule	Production Planner	Scenario 1
GOI 6	The system must be able to retrieve information about the health status of the machine components	Production Planner	Scenario 1
GOI 7	The system must storage the data related to the production plan using specific AAS submodels to be used by the production planner	Production Planner	Scenario 1
GOI 8	The system must provide the retrieved data (machine health status, plant-level systems, operators) to the production planner to make decisions and adjust the production schedule based on the information available	Production Planner	Scenario 1
GOI 9	The system must be able to analyze relevant datasets and generate proposed modifications to the production schedule to avoid disruptions (e.g., lack of required materials, delays in shipping, limited machine availability, unplanned stops)	Production Planner	Scenario 1
GOI 10	The system must provide functionality for the user to accept, ignore or manually produce an alternative schedule directly through the Production Planner interface.	Production Planner	Scenario 1
GOI 11	The system must be able to reflect the generated schedules and display them in appropriate dashboards or HMI	Production Planner	Scenario 1
GOI 12	The system must provide a middleware to store and manage data related to machine components in a standardized way using specific AAS submodels	Production Planner, Predictive Maintenance	Scenario 1, Scenario 2
GOI 13	The system must feed the assets (machine DTs described with AAS) with enriched data coming from the results of the diagnosis cycles	Predictive Maintenance	Scenario 2
GOI 14	The system must be able to execute diagnosis cycles periodically in real working conditions with data retrieved from shopfloor	Predictive Maintenance	Scenario 2

GOI 15	The system must provide functionality for configuring, deploying, and following up on test cycles	Predictive Maintenance	Scenario 2
GOI 16	The system must be able to execute test cycles at regular intervals and analyze the process in repetitive cases	Predictive Maintenance	Scenario 2
GOI 17	The system should use the key information extracted from its cycles to predict potential future failures. This key information can be also stored in the asset in a standardized way	Predictive Maintenance	Scenario 2
GOI 18	The system should provide users with feedback on the diagnosis cycles to provide early warnings about actual problems that may be difficult for them to detect	Predictive Maintenance	Scenario 2
GOI 19	The system should have a mechanism to incorporate the results of the diagnosis cycles into the overall functioning to improve resilience	Predictive Maintenance	Scenario 2
GOI 20	The system should have a mechanism for enabling the secure and efficient exchange of information between the different actors (client-provider) through IDS/Gaia-X, to share the optimized production planning and consume possible update requests from the client.	Production Planner, Predictive Maintenance	Scenario 1, Scenario 2

2.5.2.1 System Elements

The following components are applicable for the GOIMEK use case:

- Components involved: BAAN (ERP), BONOS (time reporting), SUTAN (Goimek incidents), Excel.
- Assets involved: machines and work centers on the Goimek Itziar plant.
- Needed infrastructure: OT network for machine data retrieval, IT network with internet connectivity for cloud data persistence, 1 to “n” Savvy SmartBox devices.
- Data sets: Work orders, parts & materials, machine processing data, operator shifts & working times.
- Communications: connectors for the shopfloor that include ModbusTCP, OPC-UA, Siemens proprietary libraries.

2.5.2.2 Performance Requirements

- The following performance requirements are applicable for the Goimek use case: Maximum Load: The system must handle up to 2 active users with a manager role simultaneously generating schedules for 2 distinct shopfloors, and up to 25 users with an operator role reporting schedule progress and incidents from each shopfloor, for a total maximum of 50 active users.
- Response Times: Search queries should respond in under 2 seconds, while transactions may take up to 3 seconds. Schedule generation and its propagation to a shopfloor should take no longer than 10 minutes, while progress updates from the shopfloor may take no longer than 1 minute to be reflected on the reconfiguration tool.
- Scalability Goals: The system should be capable of increasing its capacity by 100%, effectively doubling its capacity to extend coverage to an additional, equivalent shopfloor without degrading current performance.
- Resource Usage: CPU usage should not exceed 80% under maximum load, ensuring additional functionalities of the system and its components can run unimpeded.

2.5.3 Non-functional requirements

For each main module (Predictive Maintenance Module and Production Planner):

- **Availability:** the system should be available for access during normal operational hours 99% of the time.
- **Reliability:** the system should have a 1% rate of failures or errors.

- **Scalability:** the system should be able to handle an increasing number of users and requests without significant performance degradation
- **Security:** The system should resist any unauthorized access at any time with 99.99% accuracy.
- **Interoperability:** The system should be able to integrate with other existing systems for the exchange of data.

3 Flex4Res architecture

3.1 Existing architectures

The concept of the Flex4Res platform relies on data exchange between companies that act as service providers by delivering tools that address end-user needs and the end-users or OEMs that want to apply such services to their data assets. In order to realize this concept, Flex4Res heavily relies on IDS and GAIA-X to provide the appropriate building blocks for the data sharing ecosystem. The remainder of this section provides an overview of the IDS and GAIA-X architectures.

3.1.1 International Data Spaces (IDS) overview

The IDS Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM) [1] provides several elements, roles, and interactions that constitute an infrastructure for sovereign data exchange. The main roles are Data Owner, Data Provider, Data Consumer and Data User.

- The Data Owner is defined as a legal entity or natural person creating data and/or executing control over it. This enables the Data Owner to define Data Usage Policies, the Payment Model, and provide access to its data. Usually, a participant acting as Data Owner automatically assumes the role of the Data Provider as well.
- The Data Provider makes the data technically available in the IDS for transmission to a Data Customer on behalf of the Data Owner.
- The Data Consumer receives data from a Data Provider. From a business process modeling perspective, the Data Consumer is the mirror entity of the Data Provider; the activities performed by the Data Consumer are therefore similar to the activities performed by the Data Provider.
- The Data User is the legal entity that has the legal right to use the data of the Data Owner as specified by the usage policy.

The Key component for exchanging data between the various roles above is the IDS Connector. It executes the complete data exchange process from and to the internal data resources and enterprise systems of the participating organizations (see Figure 9). The data is transferred between the connectors of the Data Provider and the Data Consumer using a peer-to-peer approach.

In addition, a series of supporting components are required to facilitate data exchange between connectors; these are the Broker Service, the Clearing House, the App Store, and the Vocabulary.

- The IDS Broker holds metadata on the datasets available through each connector. A Data Consumer can search this metadata for a dataset that fits their requirements.
- Each connector logs the data transaction and sends the data record to the Clearing House.
- Data Apps can further process the exchanged data. Those Data Apps are available in the App Store.
- Vocabularies are used to annotate and describe datasets.

Lastly, the Identity Provider provides an authentication service for all IDS participants. It offers a service to create, maintain, manage, monitor, and validate identity information of and for participants in the IDS. This is of particular importance for the network of trust in the IDS.

Figure 9 IDS Reference Architecture Model [1]

3.1.2 Gaia-X overview

Similar to IDS, the GAIA-X ecosystem participants are classified into the general categories of Provider and Consumer. According to the activity, an entity can have both roles at the same time. Figure 10 provides a high-level overview of the GAIA-X ecosystem.

Figure 10 Gaia-X Ecosystem Visualization[2]

GAIA-X Federation Services provide connections between and among the different elements as well as between or among the different ecosystems. Governance includes the statements of objectives, rules, practices or regulations governing the activities of participants within the ecosystem [2].

A GAIA-X Participant is typically a business organization participating in the ecosystem but it can also be a natural or any other form of legal person. The participating entity assumes the role of a provider, consumer, or both, depending on their objectives. Each GAIA-X Asset has an associated GAIA-X Provider belonging to the GAIA-X ecosystem so no provisions from outside without self-descriptions are allowed.

GAIA-X Assets can be Node, Data, or Software. A GAIA-X Node is a general computational resource or infrastructure element. The term software covers all kinds of software that may be deployed on nodes. Lastly, Data Assets describe a data set that is provided to consumers.

Both GAIA-X participants and assets use obligatory GAIA-X Self-Descriptions. Every element of GAIA-X has a Self-Description. This contains structured, searchable metadata about concepts such as data owners and usage policies.

The identities of the participants are ensured through the GAIA-X Trust Framework, which consists of two services:

- the Gaia-X Registry
- the Gaia-X Compliance service

The Gaia-X Registry is a public distributed, non-repudiable, immutable, permissionless database with a decentralized infrastructure and the capacity to automate code execution [2] and facilitates the provision of:

1. Access to a Gaia-X Compliance Service instance.
2. A fully operational, decentralized and easily searchable catalog.
3. A list of Participants' identities and Self-Description URIs that violate Gaia-X membership rules. This list must be used by all Gaia-X Trusted Catalog providers to filter out any inappropriate content.
4. Tokens may cover the operating costs of the Gaia-X Ecosystem. This specific point can be abstracted by 3rd party brokers wrapping token usage with fiat currency, providing opportunities for new services to be created by the Participants. Emitting tokens for the Gaia-X Association's members is also considered.

The Gaia-X Compliance Service verifies the following:

1. that the issued claims are conformant to the format specified in this document.
2. that the issuers of the information are properly registered in the Verifiable Data Registry also known as Gaia-X Registry.
3. that the provided information is consistent with the Gaia-X Compliance service.

3.1.3 Conclusions on IDS & Gaia-X

GAIA-X and IDS complement each other to ensure cloud and data sovereignty for end-to-end data value chains in federated ecosystems [3]. GAIA-X focuses on sovereign cloud services and cloud infrastructure, while IDS focuses on data and data sovereignty. Figure 11 presents a mapping of IDS components into the GAIA-X architecture. The Data Provider and Data Consumer are mapped into the GAIA-X Data Ecosystem, while the App Store Provider, App Provider, and Service Provider are located in the GAIA-X Infrastructure Ecosystem [3]. IDS Connectors can be integrated with the GAIA-X Nodes.

The GAIA-X Federated Catalogue offers similar services to the IDS Broker, Vocabulary Provider and Information Model. The Federation Service of Sovereign Data Exchange is represented by the IDS

Clearing House and Usage Control concepts in IDS. Lastly, the GAIA-X Federation services of Identity & Trust and Certification can take advantage of the IDS Identity Provider and IDS Certification Body [3].

Figure 11 Mapping IDS onto GAIA-X [3]

It is therefore evident that IDS and GAIA-X can be used complementarily with each other to provide the technology required to realize the data and service exchange of the Flex4Res platform.

3.2 High level architecture

As IDS and GAIA-X have established a clear mapping between the two frameworks [3] this section will mainly use the GAIA-X concepts to describe the architecture of the Flex4Res platform. It should be noted that GAIA-X concepts are also primarily used in the Description of the Action. The high-level overview of the architecture is illustrated in Figure 12.

Figure 12 Flex4Res architecture overview

The main objective of the Flex4Res platform is to establish a data space for sharing data between the Flex4Res services and the Digital Twins of the end-users.

Each end-user production environment consists of a series of equipment and software; all these tangible objects are considered assets according to the Asset Administration Shell (AAS) concept of Industrie 4.0 [4]. Intangible objects such as processes or products may also be considered as assets. An AAS is the digital representation of an asset, and consists of a number of submodels in which all the information and functionalities of a given asset are described. Thus, the asset component in the Flex4Res architecture represents those entities on the shop floor that will provide data about each end users production. This includes software platforms presented in section 3.3. The Asset Administration Shell component will be responsible for exposing the information and capabilities of the assets through a standardized interface to the Flex4Res dataspace. The Asset Administration Shell structure is further detailed in section 3.4.

The Flex4Res dataspace consists of the following components:

1. The dataspace connector: is the key component that facilitates peer-to-peer data exchange between data providers (end users via AAS) and data consumers (Flex4Res services). The dataspace connector is further detailed in section 3.7.1.
2. The dataspace connector app: is an abstraction of the connector to facilitate integration with the dataspace. In essence, this app will provide an interface identical to that of AAS on the Flex4Res service side. Allowing the developers to interact with the ASS over the dataspace in the same way they would interact with AAS directly. More details on how the app is structured are presented in section 3.7.2.
3. The GAIA-X federated catalogue constitutes an indexed repository of Gaia-X Self-Descriptions to enable the discovery and selection of providers and their service offerings. More details on the functionalities provided by the GAIA-X federated catalogue are provided in section 3.7.3.
4. The GAIA-X registry and compliance functionalities have already been briefly presented in section 3.1.2. More details on the implementations to be adopted are presented in section 3.7.4.

Lastly, the Flex4Res services act as the data consumers of the AAS standardised API to achieve:

1. Assessment of the resilience capability of production systems at micro, meso, and macro level. More details of the Resilience Assessment Toolbox are provided in section 3.5.
2. Provision of reconfiguration strategies at different hierarchical levels in manufacturing systems (micro, meso, and macro). The Reconfiguration Strategy component is detailed in section 3.6.

3.3 Digital Twin (DT) and IoT platforms

3.3.1 CONT IoT platform

CONTACT Elements for IoT is a platform for realising solutions for data-driven processes with the digital twins of industrial assets quickly. It is characterised by its open architecture, the simple and robust mapping of business processes and its low-code philosophy.

Industrial IoT solutions need to provide an accurate view of the as-maintained state of each asset and its components, which is made up of many different data sources. Examples include asset field and sensor data, software and hardware configuration, 3D models, maintenance history, customer data and more. Based on the Digital Twin, Elements for IoT offers comprehensive possibilities to display, monitor and evaluate the history and current status of assets according to the principle of the Single Source of Truth. The digital twins mirror objects in the field as a virtual representation and are the linchpin of all data-driven processes.

Specialists can quickly implement new requirements without the support of central IT using the no/low code principle. They define rules for identifying events and the desired reactions by the IoT software without any programming effort. In this way, value-adding activities are implemented through automated workflows: for example, the execution of maintenance activities when measured values are exceeded, the triggering of routine services for defined maintenance intervals or automated spare parts orders.

Elements for IoT make machines and plants addressable and enable communication with the operator or other IT systems. In doing so, standard protocols such as OPC UA, MQTT or PPMP are used and serve the industry standards of the Industry 4.0 platform, allowing to use the asset administration shell to integrate machines as active components in automated business processes. In addition, standard interfaces and powerful integration technology ensure consistent processes across systems and applications.

The Manufacturing Operations Management (MOM) package covers the broad spectrum of production-related functions including planning, scheduling, and execution of production orders. It provides a transparent overall picture of production processes. It seamlessly connects product development with production and thus enables end-to-end digital control.

3.3.2 SAVVY IoT platform

SAVVY provides a hybrid Edge-Cloud IIoT platform capable of retrieving production data from the Edge (process values, setpoints, sensor data points...) with a 1ms resolution, as well as univocally persisting all collected data at the Cloud level, with the ability to provision persisted data to platform users over secure protocols and APIs.

At the Edge level, Savvy SmartBox devices act as the IoT gateway for connected equipment, collecting data from production assets over standard, industrial communication protocols such as OPC-UA, ModbusTCP, EthernetIP, etc., as well as more obscure or niche communication protocols. The Savvy SmartBox is also capable of interfacing with enterprise-level systems (MES, ERP, etc.) and, through container-based technology and orchestration, is able to implement bespoke logic and algorithms to interoperate with the aforementioned equipment and systems if necessary.

Figure 13 - Savvy SmartBox features

At the Cloud level, the Savvy Industrial Cloud handles inbound data relayed from the SmartBox devices, and remotely manages the configuration thereof – including definition and deployment of docker-based

custom applications, able to be deployed on the Edge. The platform comprises several servers for handling the reception of inbound data, its storage and access based on permissions, and its provision through a secure REST API. Data persisted on the platform can be accessed by either human users (through bespoke or template-based dashboards and visualizations) or automated clients (through adequately configured permissions and API tokens).

In addition, Savvy has the ability to dynamically expand the Cloud platform to deploy additional servers for specific purposes, such as the hosting of AAS and Dataspace connectors and related applications.

Figure 14 - Savvy Industrial Cloud architecture

GOIMEK currently leverages the SAVVY IIoT platform for monitoring their production processes and assets, and for analysing all the process and enterprise data originating in their plants. Data is currently collected through:

- ModbusTCP
- OPC UA
- Heidenhain TNC
- SFTP (binary files)

During the project, the platform will be expanded to include:

- An AI-augmented **production planner** that factors in both current and historical process data alongside production orders and process routes from GOIMEK's ERP systems to generate flexible production schedules that can be visualized at the Edge level.
- An **AAS layer** comprising both Cloud and Edge components, to reflect and break down the hierarchy and functional layers of GOIMEK assets to facilitate access and sharing of asset data.
- A **Dataspace layer** connecting to GOIMEK assets, to integrate and share specific production data with other project partners either directly related to the use-case (IDEKO, SORALUCE), or different actors from the rest of the use-cases depending on data-flow requirements.

3.3.3 BEIA IoT platform

BEIA will use Grafana for the analytics of sensor data collection and MQTT protocol integration between the data visualisation platforms and specific IoT devices, primarily sensors.

The software will be divided into 3 parts:

1. The collection of data from sensors using a Raspberry Pi and Arrowhead Tools for Orchestration of services

2. Sending the acquired data to platforms using the MQTT protocol and pre-processing using Node-Red
3. Analysing the data on the platform using a Grafana plugin

The code must be modified to send the data to the Grafana platform from other data sources. This can be simply done by using Arrowhead Tools (Node-RED) and modifying the MQTT topic & host.

```
const mHost = "mqtt.beia-telemetrie.ro"
```

```
const mTopic = "training/rpi/example_of_topic"
```

The script can be executed in a terminal. Data visualisation in Grafana can be done using time series Graphs. Multiple graphs can be done for temperature, humidity, and other necessary sensors down the line. Figure 13 and Figure 14 provide some examples.

Figure 13 Temperature data visualisation presented in Grafana

Figure 14 Humidity data visualisation presented in Grafana

- The x axes show the temperature and humidity levels respectively.
- The y axes show the time when the data was sent to the Grafana platform.

Software artifacts available on GitHub:

1. A simple Node.js script sends JSON with random temperature and humidity values over MQTT
2. A script running on the Raspberry Pi to send sensor data via MQTT to the Grafana platform

Also, BEIA can provide solutions for handling data acquisition, data mining and data analytics to generate a preventive and predictive maintenance plan.

The collection of sensor data is facilitated by a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC), which is subject to interrogation via the Profinet communication protocol. The communication protocol possesses an inherent mechanism that guarantees the quality of data, detecting and indicating faulty data and communication packets. Similarly, the transmission of equipment parameters such as motors and conveyors through alternative protocols, such as Modbus, follows the principle. A protocol simulator will be employed to conduct a comparative analysis between the values obtained from the programmable logic controller (PLC) and those acquired from the simulator. It is worth noting that in the Modbus protocol, various implementations may feature distinct frame formats, which could potentially result in the misinterpretation of the received values. The programmable logic controller (PLC) employs relay-based mechanisms to execute logical operations on digital signals. In the case of analog values, the data is transformed from its original 4..20 mA analog value to a digital output via an analog-to-digital converter (ADC), resulting in values within the range of 0 to 27648. Within the ADC module, the identification of suboptimal data quality can be readily accomplished through the reception of values that fall outside of the established range.

3.4 Asset Administration Shell (AAS)

The AAS consists of one or more submodels, so-called AAS submodels [14], which are used case-specifically. An essential submodel here is, for example, the nameplate. The nameplate contains all the information for marking and recognizing the asset (or product). The submodels are developed, enhanced, adapted or extended by the corresponding working groups in the International Digital Twin Association (IDTA) [15]. In addition to the Nameplate, the submodels include ContactInformation, FunctionalSafety, CarbonFootprint and TimeseriesData. The AAS itself comes in different flavors, ranging from file-based (AAS Level 1) to API-based (AAS Level 2) to autonomous behavior (AAS Level 3). It can be used specifically for different use cases, from manual to partially and highly automated production. The CONTACT platform itself offers basic functionalities such as the management of documents by subject objects or the enrichment of objects by features of a classification class. The latter was used to map the submodels of the AAS in the system in accordance with the IDTA specifications [16], while the former enables files to be managed in the form of common formats and to reference these in the context of the classification.

CONTACT Universal Classification provides a flexible and freely configurable classification system for any object. This classification system makes it possible to add features to objects and make them searchable on the *CONTACT Elements* platform. Thereby, a global feature catalog is accessed and managed. The characteristics are grouped into classes, which can be arranged hierarchically. By assigning one or more classes, an object receives the corresponding properties. A first step in the project is to generate and break down the AASX (file-based AAS Type 1) based on the BaSyx Python SDK, and on the other hand to provide the mapping between the properties of the AAS submodels and the *CONTACT Elements* own *Universal Classification* module.

By integrating the functionality of the so-called *Power Application* of the *CONTACT Software* subsidiary CAIQ, the AAS export/import mechanisms were automated on the basis of a low-code approach, so that on the one hand, these could be executed user- or system-controlled, and on the other hand the user-friendliness was improved by executing the mechanisms via corresponding widgets on the asset and selecting which submodels should be included or read out.

Figure 15 shows the structure of the AAS in Flex4Res of the CONTACT Elements Platform. To access the AAS submodels an implementation for the export and import of AASX files (file-based AAS Type 1) is already available on the *CONTACT Elements* platform, which is illustrated in the upper part of figure 15. On the one hand, in the case of the export, these should be generated on the basis of the information of an asset managed in the context of *CONTACT for Elements for IoT*, or, in the case of the Import, existing assets should be enriched with information from the AASX file, or new assets should be automatically created in the platform with the information initially provided. The lower part of Figure 15 shows the REST-based exchange of the AAS, which will be targeted in future releases of CONTACT Software.

Figure 15 Asset Administration Shell structure in Flex4Res

The submodels Nameplate, TechnicalData and ContactInformation are already implemented in the CONTACT Elements for IoT platform and are released with version 15.8. Additional submodels relevant to the use cases (e.g., Capability) will be identified in further detail. The submodels are implemented as classification classes and it is currently under construction to make the submodules accessible via REST-API (AAS type 2).

Following the same approach, each use case will rely on the same concept, using the most suitable IoT platforms and implementations for their specific requirements.

3.5 Resilience assessment toolbox

Figure 16 illustrates the architecture of the Resilience assessment toolbox. More specifically, the Resilience assessment toolbox will interact with the Flex4Res dataspace in order to access AAS data from the shop floor of the end-users. The Flex4Res dataspace provides an abstraction of the connector through the Dataspace Connector App.

The data space app client is responsible for reading the ASS data and feeding it to the appropriate tool, i.e., Resilience assessment for supply chain and factory level (Task 3.2) or Resilience assessment for shop-floor and resource level (Task 3.3). Each of these two main components will be explained in detail in the next subsections. Firstly, a description of the resilience data models will be given and then the architecture will be explained in detail.

Figure 16 Resilience assessment toolbox architecture overview

3.5.1 Resilience Data Model

The Resilience data model will be developed in Task 3.1 and this task aims to enable cross-company usage of the digital resilience services that form the resilience assessment toolbox. The resilience data model will also be used to exchange data with the reconfiguration strategy toolbox (WP4) through the Flex4Res dataspace.

3.5.2 Resilience assessment toolbox for supply factory and resource level

In order to develop a tool to assess the resilience of the supply chain-, factory-, shop floor- and resource levels, there is a need to define an architecture with the components that will be needed to be developed during the project. Figure 17 presents the main components that have been identified for Task 3.2 which will be explained in detail below. The drawing also includes the components for data exchanges i.e., the IDS/ Gaia-X connector, Dataspace Connector App and Dataspace App Client, which are necessary in order to transfer data through the Dataspace.

The data flow of the architecture starts with the Graphical User Interface (GUI) where a user may request to compute the Resilience, then the Resilience calculator service will be triggered via the API component. The Resilience calculator service has an AI service that validates if the input data model contains all the required data. After that, the supply chain network level calculator, factory level calculator, shopfloor and resource level calculator will be triggered in order to compute the resilience assessment. The resilience assessment will be done using the Penalty of Change (POC) formula [6][7].

$$POC = \sum_{i=1}^D Pn(X_i)Pr(X_i)$$

Where D is the number of potential changes, X_i is the i -th potential change, $Pn(X_i)$ is the penalty of i -th potential channel and $Pr(X_i)$ is the probability of the i -th potential change to occur. After the result is assessed, it is stored in a database, by triggering a data management component. The database could be triggered from the GUI as well, in case the user wants to explore historical data.

Furthermore, in order to evaluate the resilience at the shopfloor and resource level, additional factors such as machine reliability and mean time to failure will be taken into account. This will involve utilizing data obtained from sensors installed on the machines to detect any deviations or anomalies. As the project progresses, a more comprehensive and detailed architecture specifically addressing the shopfloor and resource level resilience assessment will be developed.

Figure 17 Resilience Assessment Toolbox detailed architecture

3.6 Reconfiguration strategy

The work package 4 (WP4) comprises three tasks, that is, Task 4.1 (T4.1), Task 4.2 (T4.2) and Task 4.3 (T4.3) being led by the University of Siegen (USI), the University of Patras – Laboratory for Manufacturing Systems and Automation (LMS) and the Technical University of Vienna – Institute for Manufacturing Technologies (IFT) respectively. The developments in each task are discussed briefly in the following sub-sections.

Figure 18 General architecture diagram of the reconfiguration strategy tools

Figure 18 illustrates the general architecture of the reconfiguration strategy tools. The different components are connected to the Flex4Res dataspace via IDS/GAIA-X connectors and the dataspace connector app. The dataspace app client is the main component that will interact with the dataspace

connector app (see Figure 18). Through this, the reconfiguration strategy tools will be able to send and receive the data from the AAS models and the WP3 components. Also, the data might be exchanged between the various reconfiguration strategy tools using the dataspace.

3.6.1 AI based strategies for the effective adjustment of the operation stages in workstation level

Task 4.1 focuses on the development of a reconfiguration tool that consists of two artificial intelligent (AI) systems. The first AI which is based on case-based reasoning (CBR) assesses the machine faults by analysing the machine and sensor data from the smart tool for fault situations and types. The human assistance system assists the worker in the reconfiguration process. The reconfiguration tool in general aids the worker in the early detection, identification and removal of faults in the production process. This system also consists of an interaction concept between the worker and the AI system through user interfaces and the AR/VR technology.

Figure 19 General architecture diagram of the smart reconfiguration tool

Figure 19 represents the general architecture of the smart reconfiguration tool. Data from the shopfloor is sent to the AI – CBR system for analysis of the faults. This becomes an input to the human assistance system, providing information on the type of fault. A certain reconfiguration strategy is determined and the worker is guided to perform the particular actions. The user interface is used as an interaction medium between the system and the worker. The data being exchanged locally on the shopfloor utilizes communication protocols such as OPC-UA, API etc. The data being exchanged at the dataspace level is done through the dataspace app client.

In the GOIMEK use case, AI models will be implemented to diagnose machine conditions and machining process events to improve resilience, which could be shared through the Flex4res dataspace.

3.6.2 Optimization for enabling reconfiguration in value chains

Figure 20 presents the architecture of T4.2, where the task aims to develop reconfiguration tools in the value chain. The tools that are presented (Figure 20) are the Macroplanning and Microplanning optimization tools. These tools will be developed and used for the Sidenor use case. The Macroplanning tool consists of two services i) an Artificial Intelligence (AI) agent to propose strategies and ii) the Macroplanning tool that will get data from the AAS models as well as the proposed strategies from the AI agent.

The AI agent will be trained to propose a set of strategies that will be used by the Macroplanning optimization tool. The Macroplanning optimization tool will get information from the plant and other sources that are important to compute a result, as well as the proposed strategies from the AI agent.

Additionally, the Microplanning tool includes two services, i) diarginate information from Macroplanning and ii) Microplanning tool. The Microplanning tool that will be used will have the flexibility to be configured using the Resilience data model. In order to develop this tool a depth of search concept will be used [8], where the heuristic solves the resource allocation problem [9].

Figure 20 Reconfiguration tools in value chain architecture

3.6.3 Reconfiguration strategies for multistage production steps

Figure 21 depicts the system architecture designed to enable reconfiguration strategies for multistage production steps. The architecture incorporates edge devices that gather data from both machines and the shopfloor, as well as data from the ERP-System. Asset Administration Shells (AAS) are utilized to represent machines, the shopfloor, and the overall plant. These AAS interact with the Flex4Res dataspace through the dataspace connector app and the IDS/GAIA-X connector, facilitating the seamless exchange of data and services. To facilitate the reconfiguration and enhance resilience, a dedicated toolbox will be developed during this phase. This toolbox will be deployed on edge devices using Docker,

allowing it to operate at the plant, shopfloor, and machine levels. Furthermore, the toolbox can interact with the AAS and dataspace, enabling comprehensive control and management.

Figure 21 Reconfiguration strategy tool for multistage production steps architecture

3.7 Data Space

3.7.1 Connectors

For the dataspace connectors, an “off-the-shelf” component will be adopted. These connectors are already capable of data exchange conforming to the IDS and GAIA-X concepts and integrating with existing Identity & Trust services. The connectors can be split into two categories: the IDS-compliant connectors and the Eclipse Dataspace connector.

3.7.1.1 Gaia-X Connector

The Eclipse Dataspace Connector implements the IDS standard as well as relevant protocols and requirements associated with the Gaia-X [10]. It is an open-source project supported by several companies.

Data Exchange

Data exchange using the Eclipse Dataspace Connector is illustrated in Figure 22.

Figure 22 Eclipse Dataspace Connector data transfer[12]

The DataFlowAgent and the HTTPService can be considered as Dataspace connector apps. The DataFlowAgent fetches data from a data source (in the case of Flex4Res this is an AAS). The first step is for the consumer to create an authentication token that gets passed to the provider and can be used for identification. Lastly, the DataFlowAgent retrieves the data and sends it to the consumer and confirms based that the transfer was successful. The DataFlowAgent may request a new token from the HTTPService if the token has expired.

The relevant API is presented in Table 12. This API is used from the Dataspace connector app to request data from a remote connector.

Table 12 Eclipse Dataspace Connector API

API	Headers	Body	Description
	-	DataFlowRequest ¹ object in JSON.	Triggers a request for data to the recipient connector.

1 See the details here: <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector/blob/7b6ea4147a1bbb27c5408ae9f2e84139c3ba9327/spi/common/core-spi/src/main/java/org/eclipse/edc/spi/types/domain/transfer/DataFlowRequest.java#L35>

When a request arrives at the connector, the connector will forward it to the dataspace connector app. In order to achieve this functionality, the dataspace connector app must expose an endpoint to receive data.

Configuration

The Eclipse Data Space connector provides a default configuration, as illustrated in Table 13. A more advanced configuration is also possible, as explained here: <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector/tree/7b6ea4147a1bbb27c5408ae9f2e84139c3ba9327/docs/developer/architecture/configuration>.

Table 13 Eclipse Dataspace Connector default configuration

<pre> IDS_WEBHOOK_ADDRESS: http://company1:8282 EDC_BLOBSTORE_ENDPOINT_TEMPLATE: "http://azurite:10000/%s" EDC_CONNECTOR_NAME: company1 EDC_IDENTITY_DID_URL: did:web:did-server:company1 EDC_VAULT: /resources/vault/company1/company1-vault.properties EDC_KEYSTORE: /resources/vault/company1/company1-keystore.jks EDC_SELF_DESCRIPTION_DOCUMENT_PATH: /resources/self-description/company1/sdd.json EDC_KEYSTORE_PASSWORD: test123 EDC_API_AUTH_KEY: ApiKeyDefaultValue EDC_IAM_DID_WEB_USE_HTTPS: "false" EDC_CATALOG_CACHE_EXECUTION_DELAY_SECONDS: 5 EDC_CATALOG_CACHE_EXECUTION_PERIOD_SECONDS: 5 EDC_CATALOG_CACHE_PARTITION_NUM_CRAWLERS: 5 REGISTRATION_SERVICE_API_URL: http://registration-service:8184/authority EDC_WEB_REST_CORS_ENABLED: "true" EDC_WEB_REST_CORS_HEADERS: "origin,content-type,accept,authorization,x-api-key" </pre>
--

The properties are used as follows:

1. `IDS_WEBHOOK_ADDRESS`: The address at which another connector can reach this connector.
2. `EDC_BLOBSTORE_ENDPOINT_TEMPLATE`: Azurite local storage for file-like objects.
3. `EDC_CONNECTOR_NAME`: This connector's name.
4. `EDC_IDENTITY_DID_URL`: URL of the service for identity verification.
5. `EDC_VAULT`: location in the local filesystem of a property file related to the access token.
6. `EDC_KEYSTORE`: Location in the local filesystem of a Java KeyStore repository with security certificates.
7. `EDC_SELF_DESCRIPTION_DOCUMENT_PATH`: A JSON file in the local filesystem with the self-description of the connector.
8. `EDC_KEYSTORE_PASSWORD`: the key store password.
9. `EDC_API_AUTH_KEY`: Value of the header used for authentication when calling endpoints of the data management API of the connector.
10. `EDC_IAM_DID_WEB_USE_HTTPS`: True or False for using HTTPS.
11. `EDC_CATALOG_CACHE_EXECUTION_DELAY_SECONDS`: Execution delay when accessing the federated catalog.
12. `EDC_CATALOG_CACHE_EXECUTION_PERIOD_SECONDS`: Execution time to gather data from the federated catalog.
13. `EDC_CATALOG_CACHE_PARTITION_NUM_CRAWLERS`: Number of instances that gather data from the federated catalog.
14. `REGISTRATION_SERVICE_API_URL`: Registration Service URL.
15. `EDC_WEB_REST_CORS_ENABLED`: True or False, enables Cross Origin Resource Sharing.

16. EDC_WEB_REST_CORS_HEADERS: The value of the CORS headers included in the HTTP requests.
Usage control

The Eclipse Dataspace Connector comes with a policy model based on the Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL). It supports three types of policies:

- Permissions, which specify actions the consumer is allowed to perform on an asset.
- Prohibitions, which specify actions the consumer is not allowed to perform on an asset.
- Obligations (a.k.a. Duties), which specify actions the consumer is required to perform.

More complex rules can be defined by combining the above types. More details on how to define rules with the connector are provided here: <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector/blob/c2de1fe3ebdb6c7a9fc0dd92c9fc89f955a3472f/docs/developer/policy-engine.md>.

3.7.1.2 IDS Connector

There are several implementations of IDS connectors conforming to the IDS specification. All connectors are available in the IDSA GitHub repository here: <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association>. The remainder of this section will provide an overview of how to work with the connector, using the TRUE Connector [11] as an example. An overview of how data exchange is achieved is illustrated in Figure 23.

Figure 23 TRUE Connector data exchange overview[11]

As soon as a Dataspace Connector App makes a request for data, the connector will retrieve a token from the identity service, include it in its request to the remote connector and send the Message. In parallel, it will register the transaction with the Clearing House. The recipient connector will receive the message, validate the token with the identity service, and forward the request to its local Dataspace Connector App. The results are returned to the connector that requested the data.

Data exchange

An overview of the API used for initiating data exchange is presented in Table 14. This API is used by the Dataspace Connector App to request data from a remote connector.

Table 14 TRUE Connector API

API	Headers	Body	Description
POST /porxy	Content-Type: Indicates the media type of the body. Authorization: authorizations token is required to access the API.	multipart: form or mixed or http-header or wss ² , Forward-To: URL of the recipient connector endpoint, messageType: the type of the message according to the IDS information model ³ , requestedArtifact: ID of the requested artifact , payload: The payload is can include any type of data that will be passed to the data app connected with the connector.	Triggers a request for data to the recipient connector. The dataspace connector app connected with the recipient connector will receive all the request information and is responsible to create the response.

When the request arrives at the connector the connector will forward it to the dataspace connector app. In order to achieve this functionality, the dataspace connector app must expose an endpoint to receive data from the connector depending on the value of multipart in Table 14. The endpoint may include:

1. HTTP Headers
2. An IDS Header message
3. The payload

More detailed information is provided at: https://github.com/Engineering-Research-and-Development/true-connector-basic_data_app/blob/master/README.md.

Configuration

The TRUE connector comes with a configuration file that allows the configuration of several parameters to control the behaviour and operation of the connector. These include:

1. Hostname validation
2. Enable/disable SSL
3. Control message format (mixed/form/http-header)
4. WebSocket configuration
5. IDSCPV2 configuration

² See more details here: https://github.com/Engineering-Research-and-Development/true-connector-basic_data_app/blob/master/README.md#restrequests

³ The IDS Information Model: <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/InformationModel>

For each of the above, a detailed set of parameters can be found at: <https://engineering-ing-rd.gitbook.io/true-connector/modify-configuration>.

Usage Control

The TRUE connector comes with an additional application that enforces usage control on data access. The service is invoked before transferring data to the side that has requested it. This service will decide if the data should be returned according to the predefined policies. The following policies can be applied:

1. Allow the Usage of the Data: provides data usage without any restrictions.
2. Prohibit the Usage of the Data: prohibits data usage.
3. Interval-restricted Data Usage: provides data usage within a specified time interval.
4. Duration-restricted Data Usage: allows data usage for a specified period.
5. Role-restricted Data Usage.
6. Purpose-restricted Data Usage Policy.
7. Restricted Number of Usages: allows data usage for n times.

Personal Data: filter out the contents of the data according to the data subject's consent.

3.7.2 Data App

The Flex4Res Dataspace Connector App acts as an abstraction of the connector (IDS or Eclipse Dataspace Connector) for the developers and enables them to directly interact with an API that behaves the same way as the AAS API. Its full workflow is illustrated in Figure 24.

Figure 24 Dataspace Connector App workflow

The Flex4Res Dataspace Connector App will expose an endpoint to intercept requests from the Flex4Res service. These requests will come in the form of an AAS API as detailed in section 3.4. The app will validate these requests against a known description of the AAS, and this description will be provided as a form of the configuration of the app. For valid requests, the app will prepare an appropriate request towards its local Dataspace Connector. The Dataspace connector forwards the request towards the remote Dataspace connector (on the side of AAS API). The remote connector will forward the requests to its local Dataspace Connector App, which will interpret the request and trigger the appropriate method of the AAS API. It should be noted that Header information from the Flex4Res service will also be included in the request towards the AAS API.

The app's internal structure is illustrated in Figure 25. It is evident that the Flex4Res app should be capable of consuming the APIs of the connector provided in Table 13 and Table 14 (DC1 in the figure). Therefore, an integration component is introduced capable of consuming the connector API (DC1) and

exposing an additional API (DC2) that the connector will use to publish incoming data. The Business Logic component will be responsible for interpreting dataspace messages and converting them into requests towards the AAS API, and converting requests from the API component for the Dataspace Connector App into an appropriate format for transmission through DC2.

Figure 25 Dataspace Connector App component diagram

The Business Logic components rely on a configuration file for the IP and port of the AAS API and the Dataspace connector. In addition, it relies on the AAS Method Validation to ensure that the requested API method is valid. This is achieved by comparing the path of the request with a JSON description of the AAS API provided as configuration. The Dataspace Connector App exposes an API (DCA1) that intercepts all requests coming from the Flex4Res services. DCA1 will have the form of the AAS API detailed in section 3.4. Lastly, the AAS integration consumes the AAS API (DCA2) and triggers its methods as required by the Business Logic component. DCA2 is essentially the API of the Asset Administration Shell.

3.7.3 GAIA-X Federated catalogue

Why do we need a Federated catalogue:

GAIA-X Federated Catalogue, also known as GAIA-X Catalog, is a key component of the GAIA-X initiative, which aims to establish a European data infrastructure based on common principles of data sovereignty, interoperability, and transparency. The federated catalog serves as a central repository of information about available data and services within the GAIA-X ecosystem. Here are some reasons why you may need the GAIA-X Federated Catalog:

1. **Discoverability:** The catalog enables users to easily find and discover data and services across multiple providers and domains. It acts as a comprehensive directory, allowing you to search for specific datasets or services based on various criteria, such as keywords, data types, providers, or geographical locations.
2. **Interoperability:** GAIA-X aims to promote interoperability and seamless data exchange between different platforms and domains. The catalog plays a crucial role in enabling this interoperability by providing standardized metadata and information about the available

datasets and services. It helps users understand the capabilities and compatibility of different resources, facilitating integration and collaboration between various stakeholders.

3. **Data Sovereignty:** GAIA-X emphasizes the importance of data sovereignty, ensuring that users have control over their data and can decide where and how it is stored and processed. The federated catalog allows data providers to specify their data governance policies, including access rights, usage restrictions, and compliance requirements. This transparency and control help users make informed decisions about data usage and ensure compliance with regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
4. **Trust and Security:** Trust is a fundamental aspect of data sharing and collaboration. The GAIA-X Catalog incorporates mechanisms to ensure the security and trustworthiness of the data and services it lists. It includes information about data protection measures, security certifications, and trust frameworks that providers adhere to. By having access to this information, users can assess the trustworthiness of the resources and make informed choices when selecting data or services.
5. **Scalability and Diversity:** GAIA-X aims to create a vibrant and diverse ecosystem of data and service providers. The federated catalog allows providers of all sizes, from large enterprises to small startups, to list and promote their offerings. This inclusivity fosters innovation, encourages competition, and provides users with a wide range of options to choose from. The catalog's scalability ensures that as the GAIA-X ecosystem grows, it can accommodate a growing number of resources and users.

Overall, the GAIA-X Federated Catalogue plays a vital role in promoting data discovery, interoperability, trust, and data sovereignty within the GAIA-X ecosystem. It enables users to find and utilize resources from various providers while maintaining control over their data and adhering to security and compliance requirements.

It would also be possible to use the same platform as EuProGigant is using as a catalog (Onlineshop) to cover the 5 points from above, this solution is also GAIA-X compliant and is based on Web3 technology and the ocean protocol (see [https://github.com/deltaDAO/Ocean-Protocol-Use-Cases/blob/main/markdown/Ocean Protocol Use Case-Gaia-X.md](https://github.com/deltaDAO/Ocean-Protocol-Use-Cases/blob/main/markdown/Ocean%20Protocol%20Use%20Case-Gaia-X.md))

What is the Gaia-X Federator in detail:

According to the definition of Gaia-X, the association is a Federation comprised of Participants who collaborate on an equal level. The Federation is not owned by any specific entity; instead, Participants cooperate based on shared rules. Within the Federation, a Participant or an external service supplier can be designated as the Federator, responsible for facilitating coordination among the group and providing necessary operational Federation Services. Gaia-X Federations are formed based on different industries and can include a large group of Participants.

The functioning of the Federations relies on Self-Descriptions, which can be understood as user profiles for all Participants and their respective service offerings, if applicable. Participants are requested to share information about their business, data, and service offerings in their Self-Descriptions, which can be verified by others within the Federation. Each Federation can maintain a Services Catalog, which serves as a repository for all Self-Descriptions offered within that Federation. The access rights to the Services Catalog are determined by the Federation's core governance rules. It can also be linked to Service Catalogu for generic public service offerings of Flex4Res.

The provided image illustrates the architecture of the federation and its basic components within the Flex4Res project. Currently, the setup serves both as a provider and federator, but it can potentially be divided into separate Argo CD environments. Figure 26 illustrates the architecture of the federation and the basic components for it in Flex4Res project.

Figure 26 GAIA-X Federation Architecture[13]

Self-Description/Metadata Umbrella

The self-description/metadata umbrella serves the purpose of declaring publicly resolvable metadata about an entity (see Figure 27). This could include a service offering, a data center, or any other relevant information. When a self-description is intended to be added to the catalog, it automatically becomes a catalog description, as each self-description is typically created for a specific catalog. Declarations can be made through self-made statements or by replacing them with attestation references, which can be secured by various ledger networks or other technologies. If an attestation reference is provided, the infrastructure must be available for the reference to be requested at any time. For example, if an ISO certificate is issued and the attestation is referenced in the description, the certificate holder must be able to provide proof when requested by the verifier. All self-descriptions are signed by the declaring party to ensure that the statements are not tampered with. Optionally, the declaration can be eIDAS compliant, requiring the use of eIDAS signatures for catalog descriptions.

Figure 27 GAIA-X self-description structure[13]

The DID:WEB is mandatory for creating self-descriptions to establish the metadata universe within the dataspace. For the DID:WEB MUST be the following things considered:

- the key pair should be created automatically by any kind of vault
- for the signatures of the descriptions the key pair should be used to request eIDAS compliant certificates (not yet implemented, but can be made by automatically creating CSRs)
- the DID should be created automatically and never be reused by any other asset, in the best case, one DID per asset in a catalog (in this example, we just create it manually by using DID management)

The use of DID:WEB (Decentralized Identifier for the web) is mandatory for creating self-descriptions to establish the metadata universe within the dataspace. When using DID:WEB, the following considerations should be considered:

- The key pair should be automatically generated by a vault system.
- For signing the descriptions, the key pair should be used to request eIDAS compliant certificates (not yet implemented but can be achieved by generating certificate signing requests automatically).
- The DID should be automatically created and never reused by any other asset. Ideally, one DID per asset and catalog should be generated (in the example provided, it is manually created using DID management).

Regarding Provider Requirements, the core requirement is to create the DID:WEB Documents to provide catalog description references. This means that each provider can provide one or more catalog descriptions per Federation, but they must provide at least one catalog description for their offering. It is important to assign a unique DID:WEB to each asset, and the DID Management system was developed to facilitate the easy creation of DIDs through the Trusted Service Agent (TSA) and make them available to the public. An example of this process can be found at the provided link. Each DID Document contains key pairs explicitly created for each DID, using HashiCorp Vault as the underlying system. Every Self-Description created must be linked to the relevant DID:WEB to ensure proper signing by the TSA. In the given example, the DID:WEBs were created using the DID Management system and manually linked.

Federator Requirements

The federation is required to provide an onboarding process for business owners by issuing a credential in the business owners' PCM (Participant Communication Manager). Once this is done, the business owner can onboard a DID:WEB for their service, which will be crawled by the federated catalog management. All downloaded information will be checked for compliance and later added to the catalog for indexing, enabling information searches. This download process will occur periodically to ensure data availability. If someone requests proof of the contained attestations, the attestation infrastructure can retrieve it on demand or automatically.

Catalog Description - Creation

To create a catalog description, the first step is to use a tool such as the Self Declaration Wizard. Once the declaration is made, a signing tool like the TSA (Trusted Service Agent) signing service can be used to sign the Self-Description using the private key of a key pair. The signed Self-Description is then wrapped into a Verifiable Credential (VC) and published as a Self-Description on a public endpoint, which is linked to a DID. The DID should be generated beforehand along with the key pair, or optionally, with an X509 certificate in the JWK (JSON Web Key) of the verification methods. After resolving the DID document and the Self-Description, the signature can be checked for compliance and validity.

Figure 28 GAIA-X Catalog description[13]

Figure 28 contains a diagram, text, plans, and technical drawings. Please note that the information is based on the provided source. However, it's important to refer to the source directly for the most accurate and up-to-date details. Regarding Flex4Res, it is mentioned that the evaluation phase is ongoing to determine how the theoretical description will be translated into a practical model.

Why do we want to use the Gaia-X Reference Implementation:

There are several reasons why using the GXFS (Gaia-X Federation Services) Federator can be beneficial:

1. **Coordination and Collaboration:** The GXFS Federator plays a crucial role in facilitating coordination and collaboration among participants within the Gaia-X Federation. It helps to establish a unified framework and set of rules for participants to work together on an equal level. By utilizing the Federator, participants can effectively cooperate and leverage each other's strengths and resources.
2. **Operational Efficiency:** The Federator provides operational Federation Services, which help streamline the functioning of the federation. It assists in managing and coordinating various activities, such as onboarding processes, data availability checks, compliance verification, and catalog indexing. By utilizing these services, participants can save time and effort in managing federation-related tasks.
3. **Catalog Management:** The Federator enables the management of the federation's Services Catalog. This repository contains Self-Descriptions of participants and their service offerings. By utilizing the Federator's catalog management capabilities, participants can ensure that their Self-Descriptions are appropriately included, indexed, and searchable within the federation. This enhances the visibility and discoverability of their services among other federation participants.
4. **Compliance and Verification:** The Federator assists in ensuring compliance and verification of the downloaded information within the federation. It verifies that the shared Self-Descriptions and their associated attestations meet the federation's rules and standards. This helps maintain trust and reliability among participants and promotes adherence to quality and security requirements.
5. **Data Availability:** The Federator plays a role in ensuring the availability of data within the federation. It periodically crawls and downloads the relevant information from participants' Self-Descriptions, guaranteeing that the catalog remains up-to-date and accessible. This supports efficient search and retrieval of information for participants seeking specific services or resources within the federation.
6. **Opensource:** The Gaia-X Federator is an Opensource Reference implementation, this means we are not depended on one single company, but we know from other partners that the reference implementation currently doesn't cover all parts, works in all aspects, and is not well documented in all areas. If the federator quality will not increase during the project phase, we might still consider switching to an alternative solution and would also take into consideration the knowledge we gained in the Gaia-X EuProGigant project.

3.7.4 GAIA-X compliance and registry

An implementation of the Gaia-X Compliance Service is already provided by GAIA-X. Its full API is provided here: <https://compliance.gaia-x.eu/v1/docs/>. The service will be used to issue and verify Self Descriptions of the dataspace participants. This service relies on the implementation of the registry service provided by GAIA-X. The registry service API is provided here: <https://registry.gaia-x.eu/v1/docs/>. The combination of these services will be used to ensure the identities of the participants in the dataspace. Alliteratively, the equivalent components of IDS concept can be used as detailed in section 3.1.3.

4 Mapping to system requirements

Table 15 provides the requirements mapping to the high-level architecture components. It should be noted that in some cases there are overlaps with the requirements because data access and communication are both facilitated by the Asset Administration Shells and the dataspace. The dataspace component is a group that consists of the Dataspace Connector, the Dataspace Connector App, the GAIA-X Federated Catalog, the GAIA-X compliance, and the GAIA-X Registry.

Table 15 Mapping system requirements to software components.

Component	Subcomponent	System specification ID
Asset Administration Shell	VOE 1, VOE 2, VOE 3, VOE 4, VOE 5, VOE 7, VOE 8, VOE 9, VOE 10, VOE 11, VOE 12, VOE 13, VOE 14, VOE 15, VOE 1, SID 1, SID 2, SID 5, SID 12, HANS 1, HANS 2, HANS 3, HANS 4, HANS 9, GOI 1, GOI 3, GOI 4, GOI 5, GOI 6, GOI 7, GOI 13.	Asset Administration Shell
Dataspace	VOE 1, SID 5, HANS 1, GOI 2, GOI, GOI 3, GOI 4, GOI 5, GOI 6.	Dataspace
Resilience assessment toolbox	VOE 3, VOE 4, VOE 6, VOE 11, VOE 15, SID 3, SID 4, SID 5.	Resilience assessment toolbox
Reconfiguration strategy toolbox	VOE 3, VOE 4, VOE 6, VOE 11, VOE 15, SID 4, SID 6, SID 7, SID 8, SID 9, SID 10, SID 11, SID 12 HANS 5, HANS 6, HANS 7, HANS 8, GOI 1, GOI 8, GOI 9, GOI 10, GOI 11, GOI 12, GOI 14, GOI 15, GOI 16, GOI 17, GOI 18, GOI 19, GOI 20.	Reconfiguration strategy toolbox

5 Conclusion

This deliverable documented the Flex4Res system requirements and architecture. Starting from the system requirements, the needs of the system were presented for each use case. Next, a set of components with appropriate functionalities was defined, considering existing technologies, such as IDS and GAIA-X, and the system requirements. Additionally, the components of the high-level architecture (i.e., Asset Administration Shell, Resilience assessment toolbox and Reconfiguration strategy) were defined in more detail, covering their internal structure and APIs. Lastly, all system requirements have been mapped with the appropriate components of the high-level Flex4Res architecture. The content of this document will serve as a guide and common reference point for the development and integration activities in WP 2, 3, and 4.

6 References

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